

Nexus Between Environmental, Social and Governance Scores and Corporate Performance : Evidence from Indian Information Technology Companies

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Abstract : *The aim of the study was to find the association between Environmental, Social, And Governance scores and components of financial and market performance. The sample of paper includes eight Information Technology companies listed on the National Stock Exchange for the period of 2017-2021. Panel regression was conducted to analyze the association between operating performance, return on assets, Tobin's Q, stock return, ESG score and control variables. Financial data was collected from the Prowess database and ESG scores from S&P Global Sustainable. ESG score positively impacts operating performance and ROA while negatively to Tobin's Q and stock return. This is the first paper that consider the effect of ESG scores on financial and market performance considering IT companies as a sample. Also, data on ESG scores were composed from S&P Global sustainable database. This study provides benefits for conducting social, philanthropic, and governance activities towards the positive performance of the companies.*

Keywords : ESG Scores, Financial Performance, Ecological Modernization, Market Performance, Panel Data.

1. Introduction

Many academicians, researchers, and policymakers are focusing on environmental-social-governance (ESG) activities because they contribute towards the sustainability of resources. Sustainability is also the demand of the current situation after the outbreak of Covid-19 (C-19). ESG reporting aids

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investors in evaluating the investments options (Saini et al., 2022). Some of the environmental activities conducted by business organization are reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, solutions towards climate change, recycling of waste water, and ensuring zero waste to landfill. It results a significant impact on corporate operations and regarded as key performance indicator for investors. Social activities comprise gender-diverse workforce, enable digital literacy, opportunities to local individual, disabled, and wellness services to employees. Furthermore, corporate governance includes a sustainable supply chain, safety of privacy of data, and the addition of women in C-suite. It has many positive benefits such as an increase in firm performance, sustainable economy, and benefits to various stakeholders. Shareholder value is also generated after investing in ESG activities (Singh et al., 2022). Additionally, consumers are looking for creating sustainable solutions, which is motivating the businesses to adopt ESG practices as a business strategy. The number of ESG activities are continue to increase which has a significant impact on management theory and business process (Nozawa et al., 2019). Environmental (E), Social (S), and Governance (G) or corporate social responsibility or sustainability are used interchangeably for performing any of above activities in the current situation to develop its optimistic impression on the society (Khan et al., 2016). A company can increase its performance by conducting objectives in accordance to good corporate governance practices and establishing strong relations with the community (Foote et al., 2010).

After implementation of UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Businesses are likewise worried about how their operations may affect society (Maas & Reniers, 2014). Nowadays, most of the business organization are practicing environmental, social, and governance activities for sustainability of the organization. It also leads to long-term survival of the business concern (Laskar & Maji, 2016). As far as various stakeholders are also interested in ESG reporting. Companies are also disclosing all their ESG activities performed within a financial year in the sustainability report annexed with annual report. ESG reporting assists in strengthening the brand of the business and consequently increases firm performance and reduces risk (Brammer & Pavelin, 2006). It is also a good indicator for augmentation in shareholder's wealth.

ESG and business financial performance have been widely studied in numerous earlier research reports (El Khoury et al., 2021; Chelawat & Trivedi, 2016; Ahmad et al., 2021, Duque-Grisales & Aguilera-Caracuel, 2021; Dalal & Thaker, 2019; Tamayo-Torres et al., 2019) and provided controversial results. Studies from the

previous academic literature indicate a positive relationship between ESG and CFP (Ahmad et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2019), some of them shows negative relationship between ESG and CFP (Duque-Grisales & Aguilera-Caracuel, 2021; Rajesh & Rajendran, 2020; Sachin & Rajesh, 2022). There was some research work that clearly indicate no relationship between ESG and CFP. Results can't be generalized due to numerous relationships occurred in the extant literature. This study is conducted to fill the gap w.r.t. Indian context. The study's primary goal is to determine how market value in the information technology sector relates to ESG and CFP of IT sector from the period of 2017-2021. The results show positive relationship between ESG scores and corporate financial performance and negative relationship between ESG score and market performance. This study analyses the additional key aspects from the literature yet studied very less as compared to CFP. Market performance is also important to identify the impact of ESG score. Tobin's Q ratio and stock return both are considered as components of market performance (Luo & Bhattacharya, 2006).

The study is outlined in five segments. Section 1 described the ESG and firm performance. Section 2 highlights the theoretical concept and previous literature, sections 3 explain the data and methodology part. Section 4 shows the outcome of the hypotheses, and section 5 discusses conclusion, research implications, and future scope of the research paper.

2. Theoretical Background and Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical Background

Our model was constructed based on the theory named as the ecological modernization theory (Hajer, 1995), which outlines the advantages of sustainability for the economy. This theory describes the implementation of environmentally friendly ways of business operations and economic growth and also builds the groundwork for many innovative processes like sustainable supply chain management, cleaner technologies and so forth. The theory also concludes the socio-cultural facets of economy (Mol & Spaargaren, 2000). The theory urges the heterogeneity, as the imprint of ecological modernization is operated in multilevel structure comprising market, entrepreneurs, society and government. Hence, considering the IT companies, the investors aims competitive advantage of the operations through sustainability and performing social responsibility (Rajesh & Rajendran, 2020).

The theory of ecological modernization has confronted the traditional view of the business organizations in order to embark on a road of long-term sustainable development, it is imperative to re-organize the business organizations. The author has utilized this theory for testing the relationship of sustainability performance evaluated using ESG scores and financial performance of the IT companies. This theory also suggests that the mix of ecology and economy can improve the financial performance by making productive use of natural resources. The author's assumption is that a company's financial performance and its sustainability performance are positively correlated. The sustainability performance of the firm is measured using ESG scores provided by S&P Global database.

2.2. Literature Review

The effect of a company's ESG performance on its financial performance has been examined in many previous academic literatures. According to the literature, researchers have used a variety of terminologies that can be widely related as ESG scores. It was concluded from the studies that data for measurement of ESG score has been gathered through survey tools, annual reports from specific companies, Fortune 500 rankings, content analysis of CSR reports, and other approaches.

(Hemlata Chelawat, 2016) researcher collected data of ESG from S & P index which is the first company measures 127 indicators. The study helps investors in the identification of companies when ESG risk is less and good financial performance seen. All firms should be required to provide sustainability information, and reporting formats should be standardized to enable meaningful comparisons when a company assesses the ESG components' potential to generate value over the long run.

(Yaghoub Abdi, 2022) researcher categorize environmental in resource, innovation, emission used, and social in human rights, product, workforce, community, the government in Corporate social responsibility, management, and shareholders. Data collected from the Thomson Reuters database and annual reports of the airline industry. The involvement of ESG in the air-line in this project could benefit the company.

(Duque-Grisales & Aguilera-Caracuel, 2021) The researcher examines the relationship between ESG and the financial performance of MNCs in America. According to the researcher, ESG and FP is the negatively correlated but

moderating effects of diversification and financial slack is directly impact on FP of firm and ESG.

(Fatemi et al., 2018) It can be concluded that ESG strengths raise company value, while ESG deficiencies lower it. Disclosure of ESG factors lowers valuation. However, more importantly, we discover that disclosure moderates the impact of shortcomings and strengths by minimizing their negative effects.

(Ahmad et al., 2021) suggested that the relationship between ESG and financial success is moderated by firm size. Compared to low ESG enterprises, high ESG firms perform financially well.

(Tamayo-Torres et al., 2019)The researcher analysis positive relationship of sustainable supply chain management controversies and market value in addition ESG is a mediator. Further, environmental score and social score has a negative relationship to Tobin's Q and has positive relationship between governance score and Tobin's Q.

(Vanita Tripathi, 2022) The researcher examines this study is important for achieving sustainable goals through the financial tools in the era of globalization. The author assesses and contrasts the performance of socially conscious indices with that of their general and conventional counterparts in a few industrialized and developing nations using bull and bear market conditions over a 12-year period. Data is collected from the MSCI ESG Leaders index, MSCI IMI Index, and MSCI Country index.

(Huang, 2019) The findings indicate a negative relationship between ESG and CFP, with the control factors industry which is having a substantial influence on this relationship. According to the growing economy. The study offers insights and adds to management choice-making and policy formation. (Singh et al., 2022) suggests organizations that take steps to protect the environment through corporate social practices will have a better reputation with stakeholders.

In the current scenario, investor is searching green and social bonds for investment purpose. However, there are varied results from the previous literature of ESG and firm performance. While examining the ESG scores, the study seeks to provide answers to the following questions.

- Is ESG practices leads to increase in business performance?
- Is ESG practices leads to increase in market performance?

2.3.1. Objective of the Study :

To find out the relationship between ESG score and operating performance, Return on Assets, Tobin's Q and Stock return.

2.3.2. Hypotheses Development

H01 : There is no significant difference between Operating performance and ESG scores.

H02 : There is no significant difference between ROA and ESG scores.

H03 : There is no significant difference between Tobin's Q and ESG scores.

H04 : There is no significant difference between stock return and ESG scores.

2.4. Conceptual Framework

3. Variables and Research Methodology

3.1. Variables

The predictor variable of our study is ESG scores for five years. The scores are extracted from S&P Global Sustainable 1 fragment of S&P Global database, world's largest CSR ratings and information database. These scores measure the sustainable performance of companies. It is evaluated by merging three dimensions known as Environment (E), Social (S), and Governance (G) themes. Environmental theme includes biodiversity, waste management, recycling, and many more practices. Social theme includes human rights, labor practices, and asset closure management. Governance theme comprises corporate governance, customer relationship management, marketing, political aspects, risk management practices. Scores are produced through a combination of disclosure analysis and questionnaire analysis of companies via S&P Global Corporate Sustainability Assessment (CSA). It will help to company to understand the sustainability strength and weakness. The Lagged value of ESG score was considered as independent variable.

The outcome variable of our study is Corporate financial performance (hence CFP) and market performance. Operating profit ratio is assessed for operating performance. Operating performance and ROA are used as metric for financial performance. Tobin's Q and stock returns are employed to measure the market performance (Chelawat & Trivedi, 2016; Dalal & Thaker, 2019).

Figure-1 : Multi-Step Process to Create the S&P Global ESG Scores

Source : S&P Global ESG Scores 2022 pdf

Size of the firm, growth, leverage, interest ratio, R & D ratio, and dividend ratio are the control variables of this study (Abdi et al., 2022). Details of all variables is presented in (Appendix A1).

Here, variables of this study are briefly described:

Operating performance – operating performance is dependent variable of the study and measured as operating profits divided total assets. Operating performance indicates efficiency of fixed assets to earn revenue. A company that performs its functions efficiently can improve sales and cash inflows at a high rate. It also assesses the relative return of the revenue on the fixed assets of the company.

Return on Assets (ROA) – Return on Assets is dependent variable of the study which is measured as profits before interest and tax divided by total assets (Dalal & Thaker, 2019). Log of ROA was computed for better results. ROA is indicating the financial performance of company on the basis of total assets. Its assistances investors and all stakeholders to evaluate the efficiency of the company and the quantum of the earnings. It is presented in the form of percentage (Sachin & Rajesh, 2022).

Tobin's Q – Tobin's Q has been utilized as a market performance metric (Chelawat & Trivedi, 2016) and a dependent variable in the regression model to assess

how the ESG aspects affect financial performance. So, it has been calculated as the ratio of a company's total assets to its market capitalization plus all of its debt.

Stock return – Stock return is considered as metric of market performance (Luo & Bhattacharya, 2006) and a dependent variable. It represents the value change in the share prices of the any company. It is assessed as the difference between current year stock prices and previous year stock prices considering dividend also. It is assessed on the yearly basis.

Size - The size of the company is inferred from the logarithm of total assets. Size serves as a control variable in the study's regression model.

Leverage – When firm uses borrowed funds then it is called leverage. It is calculated by dividing total liabilities to total assets. Leverage is important to include because managers frequently disclose more ESG data as leverage rises due to increased scrutiny from financial institutions. Leverage signifies the company's external liabilities whether non-current or current.

Dividend ratio – It is defined as total dividend paid to shareholders of the company. It is assessed as dividend paid divided by total assets.

Growth – It will explain the annual rate of growth in terms of company's sales. It serves as a control variable while testing a model.

R & D expenditure – It is the amount spent on the expenditure on research and development aspect of the company. Additionally, it causes the company's revenue to increase. Therefore, it is used as the control variable for hypotheses testing. It is assessed as revenue and development expenditure divided by total assets.

Interest ratio - It is considered as control variable for this study. Interest means a fixed amount paid to long-term creditors of the company. Interest ratio is defined as yearly interest paid divided by total assets.

Sample

This study owned several criterions to determine the sample. First criteria was to include only Indian IT companies listed in the National Stock Exchange. Then, the researcher checked the ESG scores from the S&P Global database of the selected IT companies for the five years. Afterwards, companies which were indexed in NIFTYESG100 in the National Stock Exchange (NSE) were included

in the sample. After fulfilling all criterion, sample comprises 8 Indian IT companies for the time period of 2017 to 2021. Details of the companies is presented in Appendix A2. Financial data was collected from the Prowess database. This database is used in most of previous academic literature (Dalal & Thaker, 2019).

3.2. Regression Model

This part discusses the technique used for analyzing the hypotheses of sustainable business practices and firm performance by examining the existing empirical model. The author aimed to determine how ESG ratings influenced market and financial performance through the use of financial data. Further, using various control variables in the model gives a different effect on performance indicators. The author estimated following models :

$$OP_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 ESGS_{it} + \beta_2 size_{it} + \beta_3 growth_{it} + \beta_4 leverage_{it} + \beta_5 interest\ ratio_{it} + \beta_6 dividened_{it} + \beta_7 RD_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 ESGS_{it} + \beta_2 size_{it} + \beta_3 growth_{it} + \beta_4 leverage_{it} + \beta_5 interest\ ratio_{it} + \beta_6 dividened_{it} + \beta_7 RD_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$Tobin'sQ_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 ESGS_{it} + \beta_2 size_{it} + \beta_3 growth_{it} + \beta_4 leverage_{it} + \beta_5 interest\ ratio_{it} + \beta_6 dividened_{it} + \beta_7 RD_{it} \quad (3)$$

$$Stock\ Return_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 ESGS_{it} + \beta_2 size_{it} + \beta_3 growth_{it} + \beta_4 leverage_{it} + \beta_5 interest\ ratio_{it} + \beta_6 dividened_{it} + \beta_7 RD_{it} \quad (4)$$

Where, OP is operating performance, ESGS is score of ESG from S&P Global database, size, growth, leverage, interest ratio, dividend, and RD represents research and development expenditure were all control variables for model 1. ROA is return on assets, whereas Tobin's Q and stock return were measured for market performance.

Author used panel data regression to evaluate above model 1 to model 4. The author has used two sets of performance criteria – Operating performance and ROA (Financial performance) and Tobin's Q and stock return (Market performance). Fixed Effects (FE) and Random-Effects (RE) models were applied. We first applied the diagnostics test for pre-testing results. The Hausman test

was applied to select the best-suited model for hypotheses testing. The null hypothesis of the Hausman test examines the consistency of Random model over Fixed model (Wooldridge, 2009). The dependent variable must be linked to the omitted time-variant variable in order for the Fixed-Effect (FE) model to yield results that are fair and consistent. However, if the omitted time-variant variable is not associated with the dependent variable, the Random Effect (RE) model will produce results that are unbiased and consistent.

4. Results

4.1 Summary Results

The author considered 40 firm-level observations for five years from 2016 to 2020 for the study. The descriptive statistics for our variables—dependent, independent, and control—are compiled in Table-1. The sample's mean ESG score is 1.523, whereas the OP, ROA and Tobin's Q, stock return for the sample's financial performance are 0.342, -1.398, 0.561, and 1.071 respectively. The following section contains descriptive statistics for control variables, with mean values of .209 for leverage, .005 for interest, .032 for dividend, .007 for RD.

Table 1. Summary statistics of control, independent and dependent variables

	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	skewness	kurtosis	N
OP	.342	.275	0.275	2.818	9.96	40
ROA	-1.398	-1.386	0.288	.072	2.14	40
TobinsQ	.561	.584	0.270	-1.975	10.533	40
return	1.071	.08	2.646	.613	3.199	40
ESGS	1.523	1.704	0.486	-1.894	6.606	32
size	11.39	11.517	0.530	-.26	1.432	40
growth	9.968	7.795	10.157	1.209	4.647	40
leverage	.209	.22	0.074	.383	3.813	40
interest	.005	.004	0.005	1.59	6.038	40
dividend	.032	.003	0.085	3.661	16.119	40
RD	.007	.004	0.012	3.117	11.528	40

Source: Author's own

4.2. Hausman Test Results

In the study, the choice between the fixed effects model and the random effects model was made using the Hausman test. The null hypothesis of Hausman test is random effect model is consistent. The results of the Hausman test are shown in Table-3 for Models 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively, with the dependent variables operating performance, ROA, Tobin's Q, and stock return on independent variable ESG score. It shows the p-value less than 0.05 for model 1 and model 2. Hence, null hypotheses were rejected and fixed effect model is applicable in model 1 and model 2. P-value is more than 0.05 for model 3 and model 4 therefore, null hypotheses were accepted and random effect model was applied in model 3 and model 4.

Table 2. Summarizes correlation matrix for control, independent and dependent variables

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
(1) OP	1.000										
(2) ROA	0.508	1.000									
(3) TobinsQ	0.324	0.498	1.000								
(4) Return	-0.023	-0.135	-0.278	1.000							
(5) ESGS	-0.102	-0.183	-0.149	0.011	1.000						
(6) Size	-0.262	-0.127	-0.126	0.024	0.728	1.000					
(7) Growth	-0.223	0.033	0.024	0.090	-0.131	-0.048	1.000				
(8) Leverage	-0.270	-0.417	-0.079	0.313	0.245	0.175	0.211	1.000			
(9) Interest	-0.260	-0.236	-0.192	0.270	0.039	-0.134	0.061	0.473	1.000		
(10) Dividend	0.289	0.470	0.180	-0.215	-0.193	-0.311	-0.270	-0.408	-0.214	1.000	
(11) RD	0.915	0.329	0.190	-0.102	-0.098	-0.257	-0.318	-0.295	-0.251	0.443	1.000

Source: Author's own

Table – 3. Hausman (1978) specification test

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Chi-square test value	22.224	20.247	10.047	1.92
P-value	.001	.003	.123	.927

Source: Author's own

4.3. Regression Analysis

Table-4 presents the findings of the static panel regression model considering Fixed Effect (FE) and Random Effect (RE) models for the dependent variables, operating performance, ROA, Tobin's Q, and stock return. The contribution of

each independent variable to predicting the variance in the dependent variable, given that the other predictor variables are held constant, is shown in the coefficient column. The coefficient values read with the p-value show a substantial positive relationship between the ESG scores on two of the dependent variables, OP, ROA, and negative relationship with Tobin's Q, and no relationship with stock return at a 0.05 level. Results provided by static model shows firm-level observations, assuming that these observations remain unchanged over time.

The following equations illustrate the model-established link between the dependent and predictor variables.

$$OP_{it} = 4.28 + (0.053) ESGS_{it} + (-0.371) size_{it} + (0) growth_{it} + (0.661) leverage_{it} + (-3.942) interest\ ratio_{it} + (-1.274) dividened_{it} + (19.063) RD_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$ROA_{it} = (9.207) + (.115) ESGS_{it} + (-.963) size_{it} + (-.001) growth_{it} + (1.087) leverage_{it} + (-3.389) interest\ ratio_{it} + (1.09) dividened_{it} + (-2.208) RD_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$Tobin's\ Q_{it} = (.651) + (-.068) ESGS_{it} + (-.007) size_{it} + (.002) growth_{it} + (.522) leverage_{it} + (-11.722) interest\ ratio_{it} + (.593) dividened_{it} + (3.13) RD_{it} \quad (3)$$

$$Return_{it} = (-5.14) + (-.721) ESGS_{it} + (-.44) size_{it} + (-.004) growth_{it} + (9.926) leverage_{it} + (108.786) interest\ ratio_{it} + (-5.673) dividened_{it} + (16.725) RD_{it} \quad (4)$$

Table 4. Regression results

Variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4	
	FE	OP	FE	ROA	RE	Tobin's Q	RE	Return
ESGS	0.039**	0.053	.074*	.115	-.418	-.068	.679	.721
Size	.005***	-.371	0.004***	-0.963	-.348	-.007	.796	.44
Growth	0.788	0	.766	-.001	-.011	.002	.953	.004
Leverage	0.008***	.661	.072*	1.087	-1.675	.522	.365	9.926
Interest	0.061*	-3.942	.507	-3.389	-40.697	-11.722	.452	108.786
Dividend	0.00***	-1.274	.005***	1.09	-1.704	.593	.621	-5.673
RD	0.00***	19.063	.288	-2.208	-7.906	3.13	.761	16.725
Constant	.004***	4.28	.011**	9.207	-2.969	.651	.776	-5.14
Observation	32		32		32		32	
R-squared	0.986		0.570		0.094		0.135	
chi2					2.496		3.730	
p-value	0.000		0.012		0.927		.810	
F-test	175.312		3.223					

Note: t statistics in parenthesis *** p<.001, ** p<.05, * p<.10

Source: Author's own

5. Conclusion

The research marks a substantial contribution to the body of knowledge on ESG in the Indian context. Overall, using Return on Assets and Operating Performance of Financial Performance, it can be inferred that there is a relationship between ESG Score and Financial Performance. The analysis is more effective when financial performance is evaluated using a variety of metrics like market and accounting measures used in this study. The author attempts to find out the relationship between ESG scores, financial and market performance to assist managers in formulating business strategies for both short-term and long-term. Long-term plans have been successful and profitable for the business organizations. Sustainable business practices are being carried out in nations like India, benefiting the society and the environment. The aim of our study is to provide managers with knowledge on how to increase the value of their business by establishing policies for corporate social responsibility, environmental, social, and governance activities. This can be achieved by including innovative sustainable practices of business operations through different ways like social supply chain management, greenwashing, and reduction in the usage of carbon components. This study also confirms the improvement of business reputation through investing in environmental, social and governance activities (Sachin & Rajesh, 2022; Tamayo-Torres et al., 2019). The findings unambiguously show that investors choose businesses with environment benefits like lower carbon footprints, climate change solutions, carbon neutrality, conservation of water through 3Rs approach, minimizing landfills, preserving the environment through biodiversity near office premises, and open governance practices. Social includes enabling digital talent and employee wellness programmes. Lastly, Governance includes data privacy and following ethically corporate governance values. Companies with reduced ESG risks are more likely to provide a sustainable financial performance and, as a result, can draw investors for a longer period of time. Corporates will have to support sustainable business models and good governance procedures in order to enjoy the investor's preference. Researcher includes in this study ESG scores and effect on financial performance. Further ESG scores can be taken with consumer behavior and investor's perception. ESG includes environmental, social, governance which can be studied independently in a better way.

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Appendix 1. List of variables

Type of variable	Name of variable	Measures
Dependent variable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Operating performance b) Return on assets c) Market performance d) Stock return 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Operating profit/total assets b) EBIT/ total assets c) Tobin’s Q d) Return on stock prices
Independent variable	ESG score	Values directly from S&P global database
Control variable (Saini et al., 2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Size b) Leverage c) Dividend ratio d) Growth e) R & D ratio f) Interest ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Log of total assets b) Total liabilities/total assets c) Dividend paid/total assets d) Based on sales e) R & D expenditure / total assets f) Interest paid/ total assets

Appendix 2 - Description of sample

Name of Companies	Core activity	Symbol in NSE
Tata Consultancies Services Limited	Software & Consulting	TCS
Infosys Limited	Software & Consulting	INFY
Wipro Limited	Software & Consulting	WIPRO
Tech Mahindra Limited	Software & Consulting	TECHM
Larsen & Turbo InfoTech Limited	Software & Consulting	LTI
Mphasis Limited	Software & Consulting	MPHASIS
Oracle Financial Services Software	Software & Products	OFSS